

Implementation of Iterative Target Transform Factor Analysis for Global Fitting of a Series of Substrate Saturation Profiles in Enzyme Kinetics

Dmitri R. Davydov

Department of Chemistry, Washington State University, Pullman, WA, 99164,
d.davydov@wsu.edu

Principal Component Analysis (PCA), or, strictly speaking, PCA-based bilinear factor analysis (BLFA), is widely used in chemistry for analyzing a series of absorbance or fluorescence spectra that reflect a chemical transition in a multicomponent system. Briefly, this approach is based on the analysis of a covariance matrix constructed from a series of spectra that reflect chemical transitions in the system induced by an independent variable (Z), such as time, temperature, or pressure. PCA makes it possible to compile the most representative changes in the system into a limited number of so-called principal components each characterizing an individual abstract transition taking place in response to changing Z . Each principal component is represented by a respective eigenvector, which may be thought of as a difference spectrum of the transition, and a set of eigenvalues, each characterizing the amplitude of the respective transition at each of the Z values in the experimental dataset. PCA and Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), which represent two closely related techniques implementing different formalisms, are the techniques of choice for the analysis of changes in the spectra of absorbance and fluorescence of complex systems [1, 2, 3].

In PCA-based BLFA methods, PCA results are used to construct physically relevant models of the transitions under study. In our application of BLFA for global analysis of enzyme kinetics data, we use it to analyze a matrix of substrate saturation profiles (SSP) with l data points each, obtained with a series of n different enzyme (or, in the case of this study, HLM) preparations. Analogous to the application in spectral analysis, this matrix can be expressed as the product of a matrix of eigenvectors, A , and a transposed matrix of eigenvalues, B^t :

$$X = AB^t \quad (1)$$

The vectors of principal components that constitute A are presumed to be linear combinations of the substrate saturation profiles of m individual participating enzymes and $n-m$ vectors of residuals (deviations). In our analysis, we limit the significant principal components under consideration to those that can be adequately approximated by a combination of several (2-3) Michaelis-Menten or Hill equations. In practice, this criterion is met by the first 2-3 principal components, which account for over 98% of the differences among the individual SSPs that constitute matrix X .

A major difficulty with the interpretation of the results of PCA is that the experimental data can be fit equally well with an infinite aggregate of linear combinations of the columns of the matrices A and B [1, 3]. Generally speaking, the matrices A and B represent some linear transforms of the matrices A_p and B_p corresponding to the real set of substrate saturation profiles of the involved enzymes and the corresponding set of their amplitudes for each sample under analysis.

The dimensionality of A is $l \times m$, where l is the number of data points in each SSP, and m is the number of significant principal components (or individual participating enzymes). The matrix A_p may be thought of as a product of matrix A and the transformation matrix T :

$$A_p = AT \quad (4)$$

If the transformation matrix T is known, the matrix B_p of dimensionality $m \times n$ that represents the amplitudes (V_{\max} values) of substrate saturation profiles for each of the m participating enzymes may be found as:

$$B_p = B(T^{-1})^T \quad (5)$$

This formalism serves as the basis for iterative target transform factor analysis (ITTFA) [4, 5]. In this approach, the idealized prototype of matrix B_p is built on the basis of some known or hypothetical physically relevant functional dependencies (target functions). Approximation of the calculated target functions with linear combinations of the rows of matrix B (dependencies of the loading factors on variable parameter) allows one to build matrix T and then find the hypothetical representations of the matrices B_p and A_p .

In our implementation of this technique, we first determine initial estimates for the Michaelis–Menten or Hill equations that define m basis SSPs that constitute the A_p matrix. To this end, we use a Nelder-Mead optimization procedure combined with the SURFIT algorithm for multivariate linear regression [6] applied to the first m principal component vectors and the mean of all traces in the dataset (the base vector of the analysis). Approximation of the first m principal component vectors with linear combinations of these basis SSPs allows us to find the transformation matrix T and the initial approximation of the B_p matrix that defines the amplitudes of the individual Michaelis-Menten or Hill components in each SSP under analysis.

The further iterative procedure is based on the criterion of non-negativity of the amplitudes. If, for any of the traces constituting the matrix X , the respective row in the B_p matrix contains negative amplitudes for some components, these components are excluded from the approximation (their amplitudes are set to zero) and the row is replaced by the set of coefficients found by approximating the trace with a combination of remaining non-negative components. Using the SURFIT algorithm for fitting the rows of this new approximation of B_p by linear combinations of the rows of the initial matrix B allows us to find a transformation matrix T that is then used to find the new approximation of the A_p matrix:

$$A_p = B(T^{-1})^T$$

Next iteration includes finding a new approximation of B_p by approximating the first m principal components in the initial A matrix with linear combinations of the vectors constituting the newly found approximation of the A_p matrix. The iterations are repeated until the changes in the B_p matrix become negligible.

References.

1. Ross, R. T.; Leurgans, S., Component resolution using multilinear models. *Biochemical Spectroscopy* **1995**, 246, 679-700.
2. Hendler, R. W.; Shrager, R. I., Deconvolutions based on singular-value decomposition and the pseudoinverse - a guide for beginners. *Journal of Biochemical and Biophysical Methods* **1994**, 28, (1), 1-33.
3. Tam, K. Y.; Chau, F. T., Multivariate study of kinetic data for a 2-step consecutive reaction using target factor-analysis. *Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems* **1994**, 25, (1), 25-42.
4. Furusjö, E.; Danielsson, L. G., A method for the determination of reaction mechanisms and rate constants from two-way spectroscopic data. *Analytica Chimica Acta* **1998**, 373, (1), 83-94.

5. Carvalho, A. R.; Wattoom, J.; Zhu, L. F.; Breton, R. G., Combined kinetics and iterative target transformation factor analysis for spectroscopic monitoring of reactions. *Analyst* **2006**, 131, (1), 90-97.
6. Arthurs, T. D., Algorithm 176: least squares surface fit. *Commun. ACM* **1963**, 6, (6), 313.